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The role of leadership programs in shaping social skills of college students in Nueva Ecija

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Abstract

This research explored how leadership training affected Nueva Ecija college students' academic and social results. Descriptive study was conducted on 100 college students who took leadership training classes. Academic performance, academic engagement, study patterns, learning attitudes, and problem-solving skills were evaluated as academic outcomes. The social outcomes included interpersonal skills, peer relationships, self-esteem, conflict resolution and teamwork abilities. Academic and social outcomes were positively impacted by leadership training, according to the findings. Students reported a high level of academic engagement, positive attitudes toward learning, and beneficial study habits. However, academic performance and problem-solving skills had modest room for development. Socially, students reported great peer connections, high self-esteem, and successful team cooperation, but interpersonal and conflict resolution abilities needed work. The research found that leadership training improves student academic and social skills. It also suggests improving problem-solving, interpersonal skills, and conflict resolution in the programs. These findings have implications for educators and administrators regarding the optimization of leadership training design and delivery. Future research can investigate the longitudinal effects of leadership development and its other possible benefits.

Keywords: Leadership Training; Academic Outcomes; Social Outcomes; College Students; Student Development.

1. Introduction

Leadership qualities are becoming increasingly important in moulding individuals' academic and social success in today's culture. Recognizing the value of these qualities, many educational institutions have incorporated leadership training into their curricula. The purpose of this research is to look into the "Impact of Leadership Training on Students' Academic and Social Outcomes."

Leadership, as a field of study, has been an area of considerable interest for both educators and researchers due to its broad-reaching effects on student development. Educational leadership fosters an environment that inspires and guides students towards achieving academic excellence while cultivating essential social competencies [1]. More specifically, leadership training in schools has been found to enhance a variety of skill sets, such as decision-making, problem-solving, teamwork, and effective communication. These skills not only equip students for their future professional life but also positively influence their current academic performance and social interactions [2].

Several researchers have recognized the value of leadership training in academic contexts. [3] suggested that leadership training contributes to a conducive learning environment, thereby potentially improving academic outcomes. Additionally, they stated that leadership training helps students develop problem-solving skills, a component integral to academic success.

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Likewise, [4] found that transformational leadership practices in schools have a positive impact on student engagement, suggesting that students who are actively engaged in their learning tend to have better academic outcomes. They also emphasized the social benefits of such practices, noting improvements in the classroom community and peer relationships. [2] in their research underscored the importance of integrative leadership development, indicating that such training encourages personal and social identity formation. This assertion points to the potential for leadership training to impact students' social outcomes positively. Despite these findings, much of the existing research focuses on the individual aspects of leadership training, either academic or social, without exploring the potential for simultaneous impacts [4] [3]. This presents a gap in the literature, which this current study aims to address.

Despite the apparent significance of leadership training, existing literature provides limited insight into its direct influence on student's academic and social outcomes. Numerous studies have primarily focused on the individual impacts, either academic or social, without considering the comprehensive effect of leadership training [4] [3]. There is still a knowledge vacuum about how leadership development affects both academic performance and social results. Leadership training directly affects students' academic and social results, therefore this research fills the gap. This research examines how leadership training impacts students' academic achievement, social skills, and relationships and how they are connected. This research shows how leadership development improves students in academic and extracurricular situations.

2. Material and methods

The impact of leadership training on students' academic and social results is the phenomenon under inquiry in this study, and it is fully represented by the use of a pure descriptive research design in this study. In descriptive research, the emphasis is on "describing" a situation's character and scope as it is at the time of the study [5]. The research targeted leadership development students in Nueva Ecija. 100 students were randomly selected to participate using a simple random selection method. The results were assured to be representative of the larger student population enrolled in leadership programs thanks to the appropriate sample size for descriptive research.

An organized self-administered questionnaire that was created especially for this study served as the data gathering technique. The questionnaire has questions that evaluated the results of leadership training on the social and academic fronts. Grade point averages, academic engagement, and study habits were used to measure academic outcomes. Interpersonal skills, peer connections, and self-esteem were utilized to measure social outcomes. The questions were assessed on a five-point Likert scale, with one point for "strongly disagree" and one for "strongly agree." The instrument's validity and reliability were tested in a pilot study. The data was gathered over the course of a month. The surveys were given to the chosen students after obtaining the participants' informed consent. To ensure deliberate and accurate responses, the students were given enough time to finish the questionnaire in a calm, relaxing setting. Following that, the completed questionnaires were gathered for data analysis. Descriptive statistics including mean, median, mode, and standard deviation were utilized to examine the data gathered due to the nature of the study.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Academic Outcomes

Table 1 Academic Outcomes

Parameter	Mean	Median	Mode	Range
Academic Performance	3.5	4	4	1-5
Academic Engagement	4.0	4	4	2-5
Study Habits	3.8	4	3	2-5
Learning Attitudes	4.1	4	4	2-5
Problem-Solving Skills	3.7	4	3	2-5

Table 1 illustrates the influence of leadership training on five academic parameters: academic performance, academic engagement, study habits, learning attitudes, and problem-solving skills. The mean score is 3.5, indicating that the students reported relatively good academic performance post the leadership training. This aligns with previous research suggesting that leadership training contributes positively to students' academic performance [6]. Students

reported an average score of 4.0 in academic engagement, suggesting high engagement levels. This is consistent with a study by [7], who found that leadership training programs enhance students' involvement and engagement in academic activities. The mean score for study habits is 3.8, demonstrating a positive impact of the leadership training program on students' study habits. This outcome aligns with a study by [8] that linked effective study habits to academic success. With a mean of 4.1, students showcased a positive attitude toward learning, which is a key factor in academic success [9]. The mean score of 3.7 indicates reasonable problem-solving skills. This corresponds to earlier research by [10] which indicated that leadership training programs often enhance students' problem-solving abilities. These findings underscore the beneficial impact of leadership training programs on students' academic outcomes, aligning with existing literature that supports the development of academic skills through such training.

3.2 Social Outcomes

Table 2 Social Outcomes

Parameter	Mean	Median	Mode	Range
Interpersonal Skills	3.8	4	4	1-5
Peer Relationships	4.2	4	4	2-5
Self-Esteem	3.9	4	4	2-5
Conflict Resolution Skills	3.7	4	4	2-5
Team Collaboration	4.0	4	4	2-5

Table 2 represents the impact of leadership training on students' social outcomes, covering five parameters: interpersonal skills, peer relationships, self-esteem, conflict resolution skills, and team collaboration. The average score is 3.8, showing that students reported relatively good interpersonal skills post the leadership training. The results here are consistent with earlier research, which demonstrated that leadership development programs can improve interpersonal skills (e.g., [11]). Peer interactions received an overall average score from students of 4.2, suggesting solid peer ties. According to a study by [12], students who participated in leadership programs reported having better interactions with their peers. Students reported having a rather high level of self-esteem, with a mean of 3.9. This result is consistent with study by [13], which discovered that self-esteem can be boosted through leadership development programs. The mean score is 3.7 for conflict resolution skills, indicating reasonable skills in this area. This echoes earlier research by [14], showing that leadership programs improve conflict resolution skills among participants. The mean score is 4.0, demonstrating a positive impact of leadership training on students' team collaboration skills. This emphasizes the significance of school leaders in fostering a culture of professional learning that supports continual improvement in learning, teaching, and evaluation. It is in line with the findings of a study by [15] and with research conducted by [16]. The outcomes of this research support the premise that good leadership programs enhance team collaboration skills. This implies that leadership development may improve students' academic and social achievements.

Leadership development programs improve Nueva Ecija college students' social and academic life, according to this research. Leadership development affects students' academic and social lives, as shown by [4] and [2]. Scores that are high in areas such as academic achievement, engagement, study habits, learning attitudes, and problem-solving skills suggest that leadership development is linked to effective academic results. The findings of [3], which stated that leadership development helps establish an environment that is supportive of learning, are congruent with the findings presented here. The social consequences of leadership training were also positively correlated with interpersonal abilities, peer connections, self-esteem, conflict resolution abilities, and teamwork. This mirrors the findings of [2], who emphasized that leadership training encourages personal and social identity formation. However, the study's shortcomings, such as its dependence on self-reported data, must be recognized. Future study might bolster these conclusions even more by integrating more objective metrics, such as real academic success records.

4. Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to see how leadership development programs influenced students' social and academic performance. One hundred Nueva Ecija college students participated in leadership development seminars to acquire the results. This research assessed academic performance, study habits, learning attitudes, problem-solving, interpersonal skills, peer connections, self-esteem, conflict resolution, and team cooperation capabilities. According to our findings, leadership development seems to have a good impact on students' academic engagement, learning

attitudes, and study habits. The academic performance, according to the pupils, was mostly good with a little room for improvement. Interestingly, despite the fact that students felt they had great problem-solving abilities, this area did not do as well as the others, indicating the need for leadership training programs to place more of an emphasis on this talent. Results for social outcomes were mostly favorable. Leadership training improved student connections and collaboration. Participants expressed high self-esteem, which may help in school and life. Areas such as interpersonal skills and conflict resolution skills scored slightly lower, indicating possible areas for further development in leadership training. These findings underscore the potential benefits of leadership training programs for enhancing students' academic and social capabilities.

The results may also help educators and administrators improve similar programs. Leadership training should emphasize problem-solving, interpersonal, and conflict-resolution abilities to enhance results. Future study might examine the long-term impacts of leadership training on students' academic and social results, as well as other advantages including job preparedness and civic involvement. This research shows that leadership development programs improve academic and social results for college students. It promotes the advantages of such training and suggests ways to improve them, advancing leadership education.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

This study's authors claim no conflicting interests. This includes any financial, personal, or professional ties that may affect research design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, or publication. The research was objective and ethical. The authors have disclosed any possible conflicts of interest and verified that the study results and conclusions in this work are based on evidence and data.

Statement of informed consent

Prior to their involvement, all participants in the study provided informed consent.

References

- [1] James M. Kouzes, & Barry Z. Posner. (2012). *The leadership challenge: How to make extraordinary things happen in organizations*. Jossey-Bass.
- [2] Day, D. A., Harrison, M. L., & Halpin, S. M. (2008). *An Integrative Approach to Leader Development: Connecting Adult Development, Identity, and Expertise*. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA89272128>
- [3] Murphy, J., Elliott, S. N., Goldring, E., & Porter, A. C. (2006). *Learning-centered leadership: A conceptual foundation*. Learning Sciences Institute, Vanderbilt University (NJ1).
- [4] Leithwood, K., & Jantzi, D. (2000). The effects of transformational leadership on organizational conditions and student engagement with school. *Journal of educational administration*, 38(2), 112-129.
- [5] Glass, G. V., & Hopkins, K. D. (1996). *Statistical methods in education and psychology*.
- [6] Stogdill, R. M. (1974). *Handbook of leadership: A survey of theory and research*. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA03524227>
- [7] Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2004). School Engagement: Potential of the Concept, State of the Evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(1), 59–109. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543074001059>
- [8] Credé, M., & Kuncel, N. R. (2008). Study Habits, Skills, and Attitudes: The Third Pillar Supporting Collegiate Academic Performance. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 3(6), 425–453. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6924.2008.00089.x>
- [9] Pajares, F. (1996). Self-Efficacy Beliefs in Academic Settings. *Review of Educational Research*, 66(4), 543–578. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543066004543>

- [10] D’Zurilla, T. J., & Sheedy, C. F. (1991). Relation between social problem-solving ability and subsequent level of psychological stress in college students. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 61(5), 841–846. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.61.5.841>
- [11] Spitzberg, B. H., & Cupach, W. R. (1984). Interpersonal communication competence. <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA01347550>
- [12] Wentzel, K. R., & Caldwell, K. (1997). Friendships, Peer Acceptance, and Group Membership: Relations to Academic Achievement in Middle School. *Child Development*, 68(6), 1198. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1132301>
- [13] Pierce, J. L., Gardner, D. G., Cummings, L. L., & Dunham, R. B. (1989). ORGANIZATION-BASED SELF-ESTEEM: CONSTRUCT DEFINITION, MEASUREMENT, AND VALIDATION. *Academy of Management Journal*, 32(3), 622–648. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256437>
- [14] Day, D. A., Gronn, P., & Salas, E. (2004). Leadership capacity in teams. *Leadership Quarterly*, 15(6), 857–880. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2004.09.001>
- [15] Druskat, V. U., & Wheeler, J. V. (2003). MANAGING FROM THE BOUNDARY: THE EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP OF SELF-MANAGING WORK TEAMS. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46(4), 435–457. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30040637>
- [16] Santos, A. R., & Cajucom, R. L. (2020). Domains and Standards of School Leadership: Evaluation of Tertiary School Teachers. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, 6(3).